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Case Report

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Management of placenta percreta. A case report

DIOUF A^{1,2,3*}, Thiam O¹, Ndour K³, Gueye M^{2,3}, Ndiaye MD³, Niang D¹, Sow DB¹, Sarr CT¹, Mbodj A³, Moreau JC³, Mbaye M² and Konaté I¹

¹Regional Hospital Center of Saint-Louis, BP 401, Dakar, Senegal

²Philippe Maguilen SENGHOR health center, BP: 29026 or 8951 Aéroport Yoff, Dakar, Senegal

³Gynecological and Obstetric Clinic, EPS Aristide Le Dantec, BP 3001, Dakar, Senegal

*Corresponding Author: Dr Aliou DIOUF, Regional Hospital Center of Saint-Louis, BP 401, Tel: 002216412302

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